

Advertisement psychology: A Case Study of the Consumers' Minds and Buying Behaviors of cellular phone user's

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Abstract

Weight of the advertisement in the today's era is very high and decision makers financing heavy budget on the advertisement. Advertisement is very easy method of sharing product or services knowledge with consumers and aware those consumers regarding his new or other products. Marketers are trying to advertise their messages psychologically in advertisement as consumer take decision after the introduction of the advertisement. This research article will provide the impacts of the psychological advertisement on the consumer mind and buying behavior and also identify those factors which effects consumer mind and buying behaviors. After this identification, advertiser can use these factors in this particular area of study (limitations must be kept in mind while take the decisions). In this research paper, primary data collected through questionnaires from (N) 200 respondents (both males and females) and on random sampling basis and supported by the literature review. This research covers the area of mobile phone. In this research paper we will find the sections of the literature review, hypothesis, methodology, finding and recommendations, limitations of the research, conclusions and references.

Key Words: Advertisement, psychology, consumer mind, buying behavior

Introduction –

Day by day Rivalry in the market is increasing and marketing decision markers trying to compete our rivals through effective marketing strategies. Marketing is consists of four 4Ps; Product, Price, Place and Promotion. All these factors have their own importance in the marketing terminologies. These 4Ps are marketing tool strategies through these strategies they compete our rivals. Small companies trying to stay in the market and large companies trying to get maximum market share and to expel small companies as they generate small companies and other competitors profit in his own accounts. Advertisement (Subclass of Promotion) is the main tool of the marketers through consumers can be informed about products, make aware of his new and other products, and retain them through effective psychological advertisement messages on different media sources the like; TV Commercials, Radio, newspapers, magazines, Internet/Social media, word of Mouth campaigns etcetera. Via media sources, advertisers inform new and old consumers regarding his new and old products as reminder, and also use different advertisement techniques as customer kept in his/her memory while taking decision about the particular products. Psychological Advertisement messages and presentation hit consumer minds and these also influence consumers to purchase either in need basis or as desire basis to purchase. For marketers, advertisement, sales promotion and public relations are the mass communication tools.

Psychology systematically deals with human Behavior, motives, feelings, emotions, thoughts and actions of men and women. Psychology discovers and explains the primary laws and principles of the Behavior and its goals and describing, explaining, predicting and lastly modifying human behaviors through other actions. Psychology of human is very difficult to measure and this varies from person to person. Marketers main objective is to attract and retain the customers and this will be possible when marketers understand the consumer needs and wants and needs and wants can be understand when marketers understand the consumer thinking psychology. What they are thinking and what they want is the main objectives of the consumer psychology.

Consumer mind or perception process starts from the stimuli. Surroundings information in any form will tell some things to the consumers. It may be the relevant or irrelevant, favorable or unfavorable. Consumer mind always want to see only those factors in the advertisement which fit his personality and his class. Consumer mind always want to find pleasures and benefits in the advertisement. On theses basis they process buying behavior decision for the particular product. Main focus of the advertisers is to transmit effective message as consumer mind reacts for the buying behavior. Sometimes they fulfill their basic needs and sometimes effective advertisement creates desires to purchase that particular product(s) and convert desires to needs.

We are watching number of channels on the TV and marketer's selection for the particular TV Channel(s) is very important and very crucial decision. Most viewed channel will charge high prices to the companies for advertisement on air and this will results high market information and awareness to the consumers and also effects products prices high. Low viewed channel will charge low price to the companies for advertisement for on air and this will results low market information and awareness to the consumers and also effects product prices low. Psychological advertisement will take the help of the target marketing, and selection of the media source for awareness and information about the product.

A main objective of this research article is to assess the psychological advertisement impacts on the consumer minds and buying Behavior in the cellular phone industry especially in Khairpur and Sukkur cities of Pakistan. For this purpose, researchers have added some relevant literature as supporting for the said subject and primary data collected through questionnaire.

Literature Review –

Memories about the brands relates with brands image in the consumer minds. They must need to understand that what makes potential consumer behave the way they would like and advertisement also have the prospective to brand choice among the consumers (Latif et al. 2011). Morden (1991) defines the advertisement is basic tool for awareness and knowledge of goods and services. Television advertisement is a form of advertisement in which goods and services, ideas, organization etcetera can be promoted through medium of television and advertisers can easily reach to wide range of consumers (Abideen et al. 2011). Muehling et al. (1993) concluded that over the number of years many process, models and assumptions discussed in the marketing, all having the objectives to understand the process used by the individual consumers regarding purchasing of goods and services when they exposed to advertisement. Adelaar et al (2003) Consumer buying behavior is based on the concept and ideas and suggest that Behavior has three factors; *Pleasure, Arousal* and *Dominance*. Environmental responses have weak association while and emotional responses has string association with buying behaviors. Both these attachments created by the advertisement as audio, video and text forms (Zain-Ul-Abideen & Saleem)

Ayanwale et at. (2005) conducted research on the product of the Bournvita in which her emphasis that advertisement has major influences on the consumers likeness. For marketers, advertisement, sales promotion and public relations are the mass communication tools (

(Kumar & Raju, 2013). Research concluded that consumer move when they have incomplete information and consciously take the risk in every purchases or non-purchases. His or her risk depends upon the buying amount and available information. More available information will support to consumer while purchasing and less the information will lead to irrational decision and risk will increase. Advertisement affects especially those who don't have sufficient information regarding taking decision. In this situation effective and psychological advertisement shooters will grab the consumer mind and loyal or first purchases.

TV Commercial advertisement impacts on the buying Behaviour of the women (Sonkusare, 2013). Social (33.33%) and personal (33.33%) factors contributing high influence in the chandripur city women decision for FMCG Products and psychological factors (20%) influence on the buying Behavior. Researcher also added that (as Phillip. Kotlar) said that Information must be collected before take the decision of purchasing any products. More she find out that word of mouth also influence buying behavior of the chandripur city women. Research suggested that more creative advertisements should be created for this area and also ethical advertisement strategies kept in mind while launching advertisement and markets should ad social and personal factors in the advertisement to influence the women decisions regarding FMCG product's.

Mobile advertising is marketing tool in today's era where marketing activities conducted via mobile devices in the form of advertisement and advertiser directly communicates with potential consumers. Mobile advertising and m-marketing are key marketing mix plans. Attitude is correlated with (Nandagopal, Ha, Balamurugan, Sathish, Sathyanarayanan, & Jublee). Messages on the mobile, advertisement through mobile Internet, short messages on the mobiles, multimedia messages are the mobile applications (Hanley and Becker, 2008). Purvis and Mehta (1996, p. 1) defined as a "learned predisposition to respond in consistently favorable or unfavorable manner toward advertising in general". Attitude correlated with technological infrastructure and also with the other cultural variables (Nandagopal, Ha, Balamurugan, Sathish, Sathyanarayanan, & Jublee).

Consumer Behavior should be considered on a disaggregate level and then aggregated over persons with great caution (Babutsidze, 2007). Hansen (1972) classification model on the basis of analysis and he divided in four different model; first psychological model, social psychological model, sociological and anthropological model. Choice process has multiple

stages and multiple products available in the market and very difficult to select one. (Payne, 1976). Lussier and Olshavsky (1979) suggested two stages; one general screening and second final choice. Chaiken (1980) and Shirai and Meyer (1997) consumer use Heuristic in the choice process. Cognitive psychology states that people are not process all the available information, systematically because cost is high. McGuire's (1969) explain the principle of 'lazy organism. Richer knowledge possessor needs less information for decision making (Chi et al., 1981). Consumer follows least efforts rule to search the information (Simon, 1958 and Cyert and March, 1963). Consumers first select the choices process (commonly two stages) than collects information (internal or external) for buying products and then share our ideas with other consumers (Babutsidze, 2007).

Advertisement attitude in terms of the emotional and rational advertising not correlated with the need for cognitive and affective intensity. Researcher finds that no any relation between the emotional advertising and rational advertising (Javinani & Shokri, 2014). Advertisement effectiveness depends upon the quality of the product, being advertisement, quality of the advertisement and media context (Idris et al., 1990). Jaskstiene et al. (2008) goal of the advertisement is to attract customer attention, measure the consumer buying behavior on the multitude aspects, while emotional, psychological cognitive and behavioral-ones plays most important role. Rousta (1999) advise that psychological, communication, selling factors and complex behaviors are necessary. Ruiz and Sicilia (2004) revealed that consumer processing style must match with information and informational-emotional advertising appeal and it can generate more positive attitude towards Brand choice and purchase intention. Positive attitude and high level of enjoyment of the positive emotional appeals are the jargons of high affective intensity (Moore and Harris, 1996). Emotions are motivational in nature (Plutchik, 1982). Older adults have higher affective intensity but no negative emotional appeals enlarged attitude advertising equaled to rational appeals (McKay-Nesbitt et al., 2011).

Targeting and information are the two contents of the advertisement strategies (Anand et al. 2009). Hamilton et al (2009, August) states generic advertisement programs has significant impacts on the firm's market performance. Yand et al (2002) observed that ease of use and access, reliability and personalization are the factors which considered by the both internet purchasers and non-purchasers. Sale of the products increases due to product awareness and this can be achieved through effective advertisement (Barroso, A. 2008). Tsang et al (2004) stated that mobile advertisement is not so

effective moderate to deliver the messages when the physical evidence provided for the products is somewhat unclear. Advertisement task is to present all information in such a way that product always stayed fresh in the consumers' minds (Weilbacher et al 2003). Consumer self-concept is about the product is the important predictor to judge the consumer attitude and consumer preference (Sirgy et al 1982). Advertisement has strong relation with consumer perception and buying behaviors. Quality means effective advertisement and positive perception (means buyer willing to purchase) are important for the buying behavior (Malik, Ghaffor, Iqbal, Unzila, & Ayesha, 2014)

Each and every product has its own meanings and they delivers different. User thinks what I am buying but not what consumer buying. Factors Culture, brand image and family influenced buyer's decision and market shares also depends upon the product awareness (DINU, 2012). Advertisement can assist companies about the product awareness among the consumers. This influence when new goods and services introduces in the market. Customer demand will be low till the effective advertisement awareness cannot be take place. Behaviour of Consumer and advertisement are dynamics in terms of practice and scientific training, advertisement using new and different techniques and primary were informative. Some consumers use brand products but first they get information and later no need of it. Most of the times brand user influenced by the sales promotion staffs. Exogenous and indigenious factors effects consumer buying behaviors but the decision will be take according to available information about the product and services.

Regular advertisement creates survival for products, advertisement is signal for products, advertisement provide hottest information to the consumer, special gifts makers consumers joy full and benefits and most advertisements are ambiguous and false (bortty, Hossain, Azad, & Islam, 2013) and consumer Behaviour varies geographic to geographic and social classes to social classes. Price discounts effects the consumers buying Behaviour and attitude, and consumers move there hold set consideration to consecration set (Teng, 2009). Consumers are price sensitive and manufacturing advertising efforts (Huanf et al. 2012). Jones (2003) states that advertisement effects in short, medium and long term and initially it shows positive results and increased to long term benefit. Brand equity dimension influenced by the advertisement (Buiilet, al. 2011). Moorthy (2005) said expense of advertisement show the product quality. Larocho et al. (2005) stated that Coupon is a promotional tool which effects consumers brand categorization, choice process, consumer attitude and

intentions toward brands. Sandra et al. (2008) advertisement psychologically shapes the attitude of society and consumers influencing the Behavior. Hyun et al. (2011) indicates four dimensions of advertising; relevant news, stimulation, empathy, and familiarity which significantly impact on inducing patrons emotional responses. Informational and positive emotional are two advertisement strategies (Dens, 2010)

Consumer behavior not changed by the advertisement but the factors they influences the like price and income effects the buying behavior and advertisement effects both male and females. Advertisement also effects for those products whose products are available (Rasool, Rafique, Naseem, Javaid, Najeeb, & Hannan, 2012). Culture, tradition, customs and trends effects the buying behavior of consumer and their choice (Rasool, Rafique, Naseem, Javaid, Najeeb, & Hannan, 2012) Media advertisement influences more than other sort of advertisement (Latif and Abideen, 2011). If Consumer expresses his/her feelings it means that consumer delivers there message to marketers for their needs and wants (Solomon, 2004). Russell and Lane (1996) argued that advertisement is magic for organization because it changes the consumer attitude and Behavior. Knowledge

Hypothesis –

- H₁** Psychological Advertisement significantly related to the consumer mind
- H₂** Psychological Advertisement significantly related to the Buying Behavior
- H₃** Buying Behavior highly correlated with consumer minds

Methodology –

Primary data collected through well-structured five point Likert scale method. Questionnaire is divided into four sections; Demographic, Advertisement, Buying Behavior and consumer minds. Respondents filled the complete data only guidance provided while filling the questionnaire. Data collected in consecutive 15days from different 200 respondents.

about the product and idea can be comes through advertisement (Morden, 1991).

Consumer buying behavior influenced by the celebrity in the advertisement and playing main role in the modern marketing (McCracken, 1989). Celebrities have greater impact that other people like manager, distinctive consumer or qualified (Seno and Lukas, 2007). Final goal of the company is to satisfy the consumer and this is market main task to identify the consumer need and develop those products which satisfies consumer’s needs (Lancaster et al., 2005). Buying Behavior knowledge of the consumer helps to marketing strategies and to understand the psychology of individuals (Perner, 2009). Advertisers hire to celebrities to provide their personality to a particular product (Kaikati, 1987). Celebrity usually represents to reference crowds of consumers which admire and wish to belong (Assael, 1984). Mukherjee (2009) argued that celebrity advertising is winning method for product promotion a Brand reputation. Celebrity certification has more power than non-celebrity advertisement and they have positive link with purchase Behavior (Hayat, Ghayyur, & Siddique)

In demographic section, only demographic related question included the like, Gender, Age, Qualifications, source of income/unemployed and monthly income. These are the most important because every consumer has their own understanding pattern and these factors effects consumers' decisions.

In section of advertisement, only advertisement related questions included and other two sections also designed same. Responses of respondents summarized in the Five Point Likert scale method. Strongly agree has one point, Agree has two, Neutral has 3, Disagree has 4 and strongly disagree has 5 points.

In consumer mind sections, which advertisement factors affects the consumer minds related questions asked from the 200 respondents. In advertisement, advertisers try to ad those factors which influence consumer minds as consumer take the decisions frequently, and insert influential effects in the advertisement in the form of presentation and effective messages.

In buying Behavior section, what factors consumer kept in mind while taking the purchasing decision related question ask from the respondents. In advertisement, what consumer want to see on what basis they are taking decision the like, price, quality, features, marketing campaigns, sexual contents, surrounding environment, past experience and learning's, discounts/gifts and effective products and campaign.

Results and Discussions –

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.748	24

Diagnostic Test 1: Consumer Mind = $\alpha + A.Ps \beta + \mu$

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
dimension0 1	.169 ^a	.028	.026	.98712458

a. Predictors: (Constant), Advertisement Psychology

Table 3: ANOVA ^b

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	9.725	1	9.725	9.980	.002 ^a
Residual	332.275	341	.974		
Total	342.000	342			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Advertisement Psychology

b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Mind

According to the results, adjusted R Square shows fitness of the model and value of the adjusted R square represents the variance of independent variable (Advertisement psychology) with the dependent variable (Consumer mind) that is .026=2.6% that shows very low contribution of advertisement psychology but the model is significant at the level of .002 as mentioned in the table 3.

Table 4: Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	8.367E-18	.053		.000	1.000
Advertisement Psychology	.169	.053	.169	3.159	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Mind

According to value of β (standardized coefficients) .169 which states that advertisement psychology is positively related with the consumer mind and significant as well but the strength of the relationship is modest. According to the coefficient table by looking at the value of significance... Hence H_1 accepted...

Diagnostic Test 2: Buying Behavior = $\alpha + A.Ps \beta + \mu$

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
dimension0 1	.252 ^a	.064	.061	.96910914

a. Predictors: (Constant), Advertisement Psychology

Table 6: ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	21.742	1	21.742	23.150	.000 ^a
Residual	320.258	341	.939		
Total	342.000	342			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Advertisement Psychology

b. Dependent Variable: Buying Behavior

According to the results, value of adjusted R square from model summary is .061 that also shows lowest/weak fitness of the model but significant at .000 level

Table 7: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.590E-17	.052		.000	1.000
Advertisement Psychology	.252	.052	.252	4.811	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Buying Behavior

According to the value of β of advertisement psychology that is positively and significantly related with buying behavior but the strength of the relationship is moderate, hence H_2 is accepted.

Table 8: Correlations

		Buying Behavior	Consumer Mind
Buying Behavior	Pearson Correlation	1	.512 ^{**}
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000
	N	343	343
Consumer Mind	Pearson Correlation	.512 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	
	N	343	343

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Buying behavior is highly correlated with consumer mind that is .512 at .000 level of significant, hence H_3 is also accepted

Research Hypothesis	Results
H ₁ Psychological Advertisement significantly related to the consumer mind	Accepted
H ₂ Psychological Advertisement significantly related to the Buying Behavior	Accepted
H ₃ Buying Behaviour highly correlated with consumer minds	Accepted

Findings and Recommendations –

H₁ Psychological Advertisement significantly related to the consumer mind

Result: Research results suggest marketers and advertisement agencies that this hypothesis is acceptable and they can use this for this particular market for mobile phone products. Advertisement significantly related with consumer mind

H₂ Psychological Advertisement significantly related to the Buying Behavior

Result: Research results suggest marketers and advertisement agencies that this hypothesis is acceptable and they can use this for this particular market for mobile phone products. Advertisement significantly related with Buying Behaviour

H₃ Buying Behaviour highly correlated with consumer minds

Result: Research results suggest marketers and advertisement agencies that this hypothesis is acceptable and they can use this for this particular market for mobile phone products. Buying Behaviour highly correlated with consumer minds. Rational decision maker will use Philip Kotlar Eight Stages Process¹

Limitations –

This research has some limitations and decision makers must keep in mind below mentioned points while taking the decisions. Primary data collected through random samples.

- Only the study of Khairpur mirs and Sukkur cities of Pakistan
- This research completely focus on the mobile phones advertisement
- All groups of the Mobile phone user and non-user
- Small size of the samples collected and they are representing whole cities
- Data collected through primary data and through literature review

Conclude –

Today's Marketers are in the mind of approximately all consumers and psychologically they have grabbed their minds and they are ruling on common people and they are like gamblers. Marketers emotionally black-mail the consumers, in effects they purchase products through rational or irrational decisions. This is very difficult for the marketers to change the minds of experienced, knowledgeable persons and those who have passed bad experience of the products. Consumer attitude, behavior, emotions, belief, thoughts and motives are very strong if they have deep knowledge and experience of the products. Now days advertisement used as campaign till consumer awareness and then same campaign move towards TV Commercials as reminder. Consumers mind think different from person to person and what generally they think, an advertiser must kept in mind while launch a psychological advertisement campaign. Good marketers must psychologically find out and grab the intentions of the consumer mind. Advertisement psychology has number of objectives but simply to hit the consumer mind (positive way) and its impacts on the buying behavior. But the primary objectives of the research are to give awareness, knowledge, reach to the consumers, and change the attitude and effect buying behavior of the consumers. Advertisement factors the like social, cultural, personal, psychological and ethical messages also effects consumer mind and buying behaviors. Consumer mind think for the income, gifts, saving, emotions, psychological cognitive, product, price, quality and previous learning's. Perception, interpersonal, culture, family and friends, brand image, dominance, arousals, emotional responses and pleasure are the factors of the buying behavior.

¹ Problem Recognition, General Need description, product specification, supplier search, proposal solicitation, supplier selection, order-routine specification, and performance review.

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